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A treatise on Xist function.

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We provide a brief summary of studies from our laboratory that establish Xist activation or repression by impairment or loss of tumor suppressor function, control of Xist by DNA damage and repair pathways, establish the Xist non-coding RNA as an epigenetic modulator of autosomal gene expression, identify the existence of an Xist RNP complex that functions in normal and transformed cellular contexts, and describe physiologically relevant functions of Xist in human cancer: in transformation, in subtype selection, in resistance and response to clinical therapy.

1 The tumor suppressor p53 regulates Xist expression in certain cellular contexts.

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3 The tumor suppressor p53 has major functions in regulation of cell cycle that are common to nearly all
4 cells (1-3) but also possesses tissue-specific functions that are less well understood (4). We discovered a
5 relationship between p53 and the non-coding RNA X inactive specific transcripts, Xist (5), when comparing
6 the whole transcription of human breast cancer cell lines based on p53 mutation status. Deletion of p53 in
7 neural stem cells results in upregulation of Xist to a magnitude greater than a vast majority of the
8 transcriptome, and Xist induction can also be observed upon deletion of p53 in mouse embryonic stem
9 cells but not in mouse embryonic fibroblasts from day 13.5 or in cultured cells of the human breast
10 epithelium, benign (MCF10A) and transformed (MCF7). Xist orchestrates X-inactivation; we show here
11 that in certain cellular contexts the tumor suppressor p53 can influence expression of a non-coding RNA
12 with sex-specific functions, suggesting solid tumors (which feature p53 mutation as a major genetic
13 alteration) in females may possess unique biologic properties which involve or feature changes in Xist
14 expression, like activation of p53 target genes (e.g., TIGAR) and transcriptional responses to genotoxic
15 insults like ionizing radiation.

16 The non-coding RNA Xist is activated by loss or mutation of the retinoblastoma tumor suppressor.

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20 We recently described differential expression of Xist as among the greatest gene expression differences
21 between wild-type and p53 mutant human breast cancer cell lines, and demonstrated that p53 controls
22 Xist expression in select cellular contexts (1). Here we describe activation of the non-coding RNA Xist
23 following loss or mutation of the Rb tumor suppressor (2, 3). Activation of Xist during human solid
24 tumorigenesis is likely more prevalent and biologically relevant than appreciated.

25 Control of Xist by 53bp1.

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We demonstrate here control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation of the
duplicate X chromosome in females, the X-inactive specific transcript Xist, by 53bp1. Thus, expression of
Xist is controlled by the two major tumor suppressors, p53 and Rb, and independently by a p53
interacting-protein, 53bp1.

Control of Xist by BRCA1.

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We previously demonstrated control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation
in humans with two X chromosomes (females), Xist, by the two major cellular tumor suppressors, p53 and
Rb1 (1, 2), and demonstrated that activation of Xist occurs in females with breast cancer (3) and in males
with lung cancer (4), finding that aberrant Xist modulation occurs in human solid tissue transformation
(cancer) and demonstrating a mechanism for this (1-2, 5). We next discovered control of Xist by the
p53-associated molecule 53bp1 (6). 53bp1 has functions in DNA damage repair signaling (7-11)

1 suggesting Xist activation is linked to DNA damage and/or DNA repair. We demonstrate here control of the
2 non-coding RNA of Xist by the DNA repair associated BRCA1 (12-14). Thus, here, we discover linkage
3 between a major susceptibility gene for cancer in humans, BRCA1, which possesses functions in cell
4 cycle control and repair of damaged DNA, and expression of Xist.

4 Control of Xist by Rif1 demonstrates a role for double-strand break DNA repair in Xist activation.

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7 We recently demonstrated control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation in
8 humans, Xist, by the two major cellular tumor suppressors, p53 and Rb1, demonstrated that activation of
9 Xist occurs in females with breast cancer and in males with lung cancer, finding that aberrant Xist
10 modulation occurs in human solid tissue transformation (cancer) and demonstrating a mechanism that
11 accounts for Xist activation in transformation. We next discovered control of Xist both by the
12 p53-associated molecule 53bp1, as well as a major breast cancer susceptibility gene, BRCA1. 53bp1 and
13 BRCA1 have functions in DNA damage repair. 53bp1 is associated with double-strand break resection in
14 conjunction with a second nuclear effector, Rif1. We demonstrate here control of Xist activation by Rif1.

12 Control of Xist by MRE11 indicates Xist activation in tumorigenesis is associated with double-strand break
13 DNA repair.

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16 We recently described control of the non-coding RNA that functions in dosage compensation in
17 humans, Xist, by the two major cellular tumor suppressors, p53 and Rb1, showed activation of Xist in
18 breast cancer and in lung cancer in humans, and subsequently described control of Xist multiple nuclear
19 effectors important for repair of DNA at double-strand breaks, including the p53-associated molecule
20 53bp1, the breast cancer susceptibility gene BRCA1, and 53bp1-associated molecule Rif1. 53bp1,
21 BRCA1 and Rif1 participate in repair of the DNA at double-strand breaks, suggesting that functions of the
22 MRN (MRE11/Rad50/Nbs1) complex (1) may be important for or during Xist activation prior to and/or
23 during solid tissue transformation in humans. We demonstrate here control of Xist by the MRN complex
24 component MRE11. Pathways important for repair of DNA double-strand breaks, and thus DNA damage
25 repair machinery and signaling molecules activated by DNA damage are biologically relevant to the
26 molecular mechanisms underlying Xist activation during transformation in humans.

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5 The relationship between Xist and DNA damage as evidenced by impairment of DNA-PKc (protein kinase
6 C, PRKDC).

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11 Double stranded DNA breaks result in activation of 53bp1, which relays the damage signal to ATM, and
12 ATR for activation of CHEK1/2 and BRCA1/2 through activation of the protein kinase DNA-PKc. Genetic
13 depletion of 53bp1 and BRCA1 by RNA interference each result in Xist activation, supporting a
14 mechanism by which Xist transcription is induced or silenced by activation of DNA damage and repair
15 pathway. This proposed mechanism requires that pathway components residing between 53bp1 and
16 BRCA1, like DNA-PKc, similarly contribute to Xist modulation when perturbed experimentally or by
17 endogenous repair activity. We demonstrate here that DNA-PKc mutation in mammalian cells results in
18 and is sufficient for transcriptional modulation of Xist separate from its development function in
19 X-inactivation.

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27 Activation of Xist by mutation of a DNA repair helicase, ERCC3, implicates DNA excision repair in
28 transcriptional modulation of Xist associated with DNA damage.

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Xist is activated by tumor suppressor loss or mutation. We discovered and described Xist activation and
repression by genetic depletion of 53bp1, Rif1, BRCA1 and MRE11A together suggesting an intrinsic
relationship between homologous recombination (HR) or non homologous end joining (NHEJ)-type repair
of DNA damage and Xist modulation in cells separate from its function in development during Barr body
establishment. We describe here modulation of Xist non-coding RNA by mutation of the genes
corresponding to the xeroderma pigmentosum B complementation group (XPB), ERCC3.

Non-developmentally oriented Xist activation and repression resulting from tumor suppressor impairment
likely corresponds to the same event as Xist modulation resulting from perturbation of HR/NHEJ double
strand break repair; this also likely includes the nucleotide excision repair pathway.

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3 Xist transgenic culture systems and Xist⁺ human pluripotent stem cells reveal transcriptional targets of
4 Xist.

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9 We identify here through the study of total transcription in human cells engineered to express an Xist
10 transgene, and in human pluripotent stem cells selected at the clonal level for Xist positivity (Xist⁺ hES),
11 and proteomic study of Xist interacting proteins a network of epigenetic molecules whose expression is
12 controlled by Xist. The range of epigenetic molecules controlled by Xist included members of the plant
13 homeodomain Phf, chromobox Cbx, methyl-CpG binding Mbd, bromodomain Brd, chromodomain Chd and
14 histone lysine demethylase Kdm families. Xist could repress or activate most of its targets consistent with
15 an imprinting function that could both silence or derepress targets. Phf6 was a transcriptional target of
16 Xist and an Xist-interacting protein, as were Cbx5 and Cbx3, as well as Kdm5d. The network identified
17 here represents a cell-type specific group of molecules with as of yet largely unidentified function in Xist
18 transcriptional regulation.

19 Males and females activate Xist differently during solid tumorigenesis in vivo.

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21 Using genetically engineered mouse models of solid tumorigenesis resulting from p53 and Rb inhibition in
22 the prostate and seminal vesicles of males and in the mammary glands of females, we demonstrate an
23 essential sex-specific difference in transcriptional induction of the non-coding RNA Xist (1, 2) during
24 transformation of solid tissues in mammals in vivo (3, 4).

25 Xist is differentially expressed in human breast cancer and its expression is controlled by estrogen.

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28 We have discovered and described changes in expression of the non-coding RNA Xist as among the
greatest gene expression differences when comparing p53-sufficient and p53-deficient breast cancer cell
lines (1). We next demonstrated control of Xist in certain cellular contexts by the two major cellular tumor
suppressors p53 and Rb (1, 2). We recently described existence and composition of an Xist RNP complex
that hypothetically functions to drive tumor growth and disease progression in humans with cancer (3)
concomitant with activation of epigenetic machinery including the Tet methylcytosine dioxygenases (4).
Here, we report subtype-specific expression of Xist in human breast cancer, describe its control by the sex
hormone estrogen and its activation by the hormone deprivation (endocrine therapy) agents tamoxifen and
letrozole.

1 Xist modulates semaphorin expression in solid tumors altering CNS outcomes, and pharmacological
2 CDK4/6 inhibition antagonizes this function.

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7 Abstract: The non-coding RNA Xist functions in inactivation of duplicate X chromosomes to exert dosage
8 compensation in females. Xist cooperates with epigenetic machinery like PRC2 to form a transcriptional
9 modulation complex and mark the DNA. We recently described control of Xist by the tumor suppressors
10 p53 and Rb, and demonstrated the existence of a transformation-specific Xist RNP complex in solid
11 tumors in humans. We present evidence here revealing transcriptional control of the semaphorin family by
12 Xist in human cancer. Specifically, Xist controls expression of a gene whose expression is silenced during
13 metastasis to the brain in humans with breast cancer, semaphorin 3C. Inducible transgenic expression of
14 Xist results in activation of semaphorin 3C. In humans with lung cancer, Xist represses sema3C
15 expression and treatment with a CDK4/6 inhibitor relieves this transcriptional control, conferring superior
16 overall survival outcomes in stage III and stage IV NSCLC patients.

17 Xist exerts deleterious, oncogenic function in AML.

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22 We previously described activation of Xist following loss of the tumor suppressors p53 and Rb1 in solid
23 tissues in mouse and man, and a role for Xist in lineage specification of breast cancer molecular subtype
24 (1-5). Contrarily, Xist has been described as a tumor suppressor in hematopoietic stem cells (6). We
25 found robust activation of Xist in acute myeloid leukemia. Survey of human cancers demonstrated that
26 like in breast cancer, Xist is over-expressed in AML. Consistent with a model wherein Xist activation is
27 deleterious (oncogenic or mutator type [7]), increased AML expression correlated with inferior overall
28 survival (decreased time to death) - in males but not females. Interestingly, Xist expression cooperated
with NPM1 mutation or mutation of the tyrosine kinase domain of FLT3 to influence survival of humans
with AML. Xist is not likely to possess tumor suppressor function in at least one hematologic cancer, or
alternatively, its oncogenic or tumor suppressive function changes throughout transformation and disease
progression in the hematopoietic compartment.

29 Identification of cell and tumor type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes.

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32 We recently described (1) a mechanism of transcriptional regulation, in human cancer and in
33 development, wherein the non-coding RNA responsible for X-inactivation, Xist, is modulated in the
34 presence of p53 mutation, or induced following loss of p53 tumor suppression, representing a novel and
35 biologically relevant method of transcriptional regulation in solid tumors.

36 To understand the precise mechanism by which Xist exerts ectopic function in human cancer, we
37 integrated publicly available proteomic data (4-9) that identify bona fide Xist-interacting molecules with the
38 study of clonal whole transcription in human embryonic stem cells positive or negative for Xist expression
(10), along with mouse embryonic stem cells lacking p53 (11), where Xist is induced, to identify commonly
mobilized genetic interactants transcriptionally.

1 We describe here high-confidence differential expression of the RNA-binding protein KHDRBS1 in Xist+
2 human embryonic stem cells and in p53-deficient murine embryonic stem cells that up-regulate Xist,
3 indicating existence of a cell- or tumor -type specific RNP complex containing both Xist and KHDRBS1,
4 and possessing ectopic regulatory functions. A key and central feature of the Xist RNP complex described
5 herein, identified through study of genetic co-regulation across tissues transcriptome-wide (12) is
6 modulation of the interleukin enhancer-binding factors ILF2 and ILF3 which has functions in angiogenesis
7 and amino acid sensing (13-15).

8 Identification of cell and tumor type-specific Xist RNA/protein complexes: BAZ2A.

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13 We recently described (1) a mechanism of transcriptional regulation, in human cancer and in
14 development, wherein the non-coding RNA responsible for X-inactivation, Xist, is modulated in the
15 presence of p53 mutation, or induced following loss of p53 tumor suppression, representing a novel and
16 biologically relevant method of transcriptional regulation in solid tumors.

17 To understand the precise mechanism by which Xist exerts ectopic function in human cancer, we studied
18 whole transcription in human cells genetically engineered to contain an Xist transgene (10) to identify Xist
19 interactants, as well as human embryonic stem cells which were positive for Xist expression at the clonal
20 level or were derived from a male or female and thus Xist-positive or Xist- negative at the population level.

21 We provide evidence here demonstrating the presence of bromodomain adjacent to zinc finger domain
22 2A, encoded by BAZ2A in a cell- or tumor -type specific RNP complex containing Xist. Importantly, we
23 found evidence indicating BAZ2A and a second gene, BAZ2B, were core members of an Xist RNP
24 complex and were present in the Xist RNP mutually exclusive states.

25 Identification of Menin as a component of an Xist solid tumor RNP complex.

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We describe here identification of Menin, encoded by Men1, as a component of an Xist RNP complex
assembled in solid tumors in humans with cancer and human cells during transformation. Men1
expression was modestly activated in Xist+ embryonic stem cell clones and repressed in cells expressing
an Xist transgene. In p53-deficient breast cancer cells that feature Xist silencing as their defining
transcriptional feature, Men1 expression was also modestly activated. Proteomic analyses (published)
identified Men1 as an Xist-interacting protein. Men1 was transcriptionally co-regulated with Xist
localization factors SPEN and CIZ1, as well as recently identified Xist RNP complex components
KHDRBS1 and ILF3, together indicating Menin possesses a functional role in the Xist RNP in human
cancer.

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Composition of an Xist RNP complex that functions to promote clonal fitness: SAFB.

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We recently described Xist induction (and in some cases its silencing), as a recurrent transcriptional event associated with p53-deficient backgrounds, and demonstrated Xist activation is directly controlled by loss of tumor suppressor (p53 or Rb) function. Xist expression is high soon after the onset of transformation; in some cancer types, like breast cancer, its expression remains high while in others its expression levels subside but remain detectable at clinical presentation of solid tumors. Xist activation is functionally r